

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YOHOU****FIRST NAME: KEVIN SYLVESTRE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Describing the variables provides an advanced organizer for understanding the constructs included in the measures described. The variables are operationalized in the measures:

- In quantitative research, variables cannot be measured by an instrument with several scales, with one variable operationalized by one scale.
- In qualitative research, variables cannot be measured by focus group questions, with one variable operationalized by one focus group question.
- In qualitative research, all of the variables of interest may not be specified at the outset of the study.¹**

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 43.

- In qualitative research, the quality and relevance of the knowledge gained often do not require a recursive or iterative, research process.
2. Which of the references uses the correct pattern in the bibliography for a book entitled *Migration, Family, and Gender in China* with two authors written by Choi, Susanne Y. P., and Yinni Peng, edited at the University of California Press in Oakland and published in 2006?
- Choi, Susanne Y. P., and Yinni Peng. 2016. *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family, and Gender in China*. Oakland: University of California Press.**²
- Choi, Susanne Y. P., and Yinni Peng. 2016. *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family, and Gender in China*. Oakland: University of California Press.
- Choi, Susanne Y. P., and Yinni Peng. 2016. *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family, and Gender in China*. University of California, Oakland.
- Choi, Susanne Y. P., and Yinni Peng. *Masculine Promise: Migration, Family, and Gender in China*. Oakland: University of California Press. 2016.
3. A style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing:
- That will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output.**³
- That will help the customers to accept you in their project.
- That will oblige you to respect the recommendation of the customers.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2008), 229–231.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 41.

- That will allow you to produce a consistent dissertation.
4. In the experimental sciences, readers expect papers to follow an organization like this:
- Introduction, Methods and Materials, Results, Discussion, and Conclusion.**⁴
 - Introduction, Methods, Recommendations, Discussion, and Conclusion.
 - Introduction, Materials, Results, Discussion, Recommendations, and Conclusion.
 - Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion.
5. One of the initial things required for writing is to:
- Have all the style guides, research the topic, and write.
 - Have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write.**⁵
 - Read more, research, and write.
 - Research the topic, validate it with the style guide, and write.
6. Only references guard against plagiarism which is a serious academic offence. It is important to note that:
- All academic essays can contain references.
 - All academic essays must contain references.**⁶
 - Some academic essays must contain references.
 - Some academic essays cannot contain references.

⁴ Turabian, 69.

⁵ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 7.

⁶ Ibid., 11.

7. Bibliographies are designed as lists in which each source has its own entry, so...
- Localization can be used without confusion to separate such elements as author, title, and publication data.
 - Periods can be used with confusion to separate such elements as author, title, and publication data.
 - Periods can be used without confusion to separate such elements as author, title, and publication data.**⁷
 - Elements such as author, title, and publication data do not need to be used.
8. For a book with four or more authors, adapt the parenthetical citation pattern only, as follows (XX stands in for page number(s) actually cited, YY–YY for a full span of page numbers for an article or a chapter):
- (Author #1's Last Name, Author #2's Last Name, Author #3's Last Name et Author #4's Last Name. Year of Publication, XX).
 - (Author #1's Last Name et al. Year of Publication, XX).**⁸
 - (Author #1's Last Name et al. Year of Publication, YY-YY).
 - (Author #1's First Name, Author #2's First Name, Author #3's First Name et Author #4's First Name. Year of Publication, XX).

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Turabian, 231.

9. In all research projects, you have just five general aims, identify the good one:

- Do not ask a question worth answering.
- Find a question that you can support with good reasons.
- Find all data that you can not use as reliable evidence to support your reasons.
- Draft an argument that makes necessary a good case for your answer.⁹**

10. Why should anyone bother mentioning the source of where the information they are writing about came from?

- It is fair to take someone's work and not give them credit.
- Plagiarism is acceptable and ethical.
- It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.¹⁰**
- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical but acceptable.

⁹ Turabian, 23.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.